

Summary of four shake table tests on reinforced concrete buildings

Tonatiuh Rodriguez-Nikl¹, Mario E. Rodriguez²

¹Cal State LA, trodrig7@calstatela.edu, ²Instituto de Ingeniería, UNAM

September 30, 2019

Report Number EBR004

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3257686>

(Consult DOI for citation information)

Overview

This report summarizes the results of five reinforced concrete building specimens from four shake table tests. These results were reviewed as part of a study to validate an earthquake damage index against test data. Each test is reported as follows:

- Description of specimen
 - General
 - Geometry
 - Material properties
- Design process for specimen
- Description of ground motions
- Description of damage to specimen
- Global and interstory drift
- Estimated displacement ductility
- Measured period

Small-scale ten-story ductile frames (two specimens)

Description of specimen

General:

These specimens were tested in 1972 at the University of Illinois, Urbana Champaign as part of a doctoral thesis [C72a]. The purpose of the tests was to investigate nonlinear structural behavior within the context of a proposed analysis and design method. Two identical, scaled ten-story, three-bay frames, were subjected to different number and intensity of base motions.

Geometry:

Each test structure had story heights of 9 in (229 mm), 90 in (2290 mm) in total height, and bay lengths of 12 in (Fig. 1). A weight of 1000 lb was added to each story with a center of mass at the beam centerlines. Columns were 2.0 in x 1.5 in. Longitudinal reinforcement was four longitudinal wires (one in each corner). Due to scaling, steel wire gauge was used instead of standard reinforcing bar (diameters are provided in the thesis). Different gauges were used in lower and upper stories with the splices in the middle of the fifth story. External columns used #7 gauge wire in stories 1-4 and #10 gauge wire in stories 6-10 (larger gauges have smaller diameters). Internal columns used #8 gauge wire in stories 1-4 and #13 gauge wire in stories 6-10. Beams were 1.5 in x 1.5 in, reinforced with four longitudinal wires (one in each corner). All beams in stories 1-4 were reinforced with #13 gauge wire and in stories 5-10 with #16 gauge wire. The square cross-section was dictated by construction requirements. However, the cores of the beams were 0.75 in x 1.0 in. All transverse reinforcement was with spirals made of #16 gauge wire, with a pitch of 0.35 in in the columns and 0.3 in in the beams.

Figure 1: Test specimen [C72a]

The test structures were not models of any particular prototype structure, rather they were physical models of idealized structural concepts. For these reasons, a scale factor for length was not provided. However, according to standard scaling rules, the time reduction factor of 2.5 used in this study would imply a length reduction factor of $2.5^2 = 6.25$. The time factor of 2.5 was arrived at by an estimate of periods: 1.5 s for a hypothesized full-scale, ten-story structure, and 0.6 s for the calculated cracked period

of the experimental model. The length factor of 6.25 implies prototype story heights of 56” (1.43 m). To obtain more realistic story heights, a scale factor closer to 10 to 12 would have made sense.

Material properties:

Nominal material properties for concrete are (a) compressive strength: 31 MPa (4.5 ksi) and (b) modulus of elasticity: 20,700 MPa (3000 ksi). For steel, the nominal properties are (a) yield stress: 480 MPa (70 ksi) and (b) modulus of elasticity: 207000 MPa (30000 ksi). Due to scaling, the concrete used no coarse aggregate. Fine sand substituted for fine aggregate and coarse sand substituted for coarse aggregate. Peak stress was reached at a strain of approximately 0.003. To improve bond, the steel wire was knurled, i.e., provided with small indentations. The wire was also annealed to achieve a constant yield stress for all wire sizes. The resulting steel wire was very ductile; test data was provided up to 8% strain with no strength degradation. It seems that great care was taken in this study to avoid any issues related to scaling effects.

Design process for specimen

Special attention was given to the reinforcement of the test structures so that shear and bond failures would be avoided and the structural response would be limited to axial and bending effects. Bond failures were avoided by extending reinforcement by 60 bar diameters, use of 180-degree hooks at beam and column ends and welded plates in the foundation. Beams were forced to dissipate much more energy than the columns, which were expected to remain elastic

Description of ground motions

All the base motions were patterned after the El Centro-NS, 1940 earthquake. The original earthquake time scale was compressed by a factor of 2.5. The design earthquake had a maximum base acceleration (referred to in this report as PGA for peak ground acceleration) of 0.5g, corresponding approximately to tests H2-3 and H2-4. For the last test, H2-7, the maximum recorded acceleration was 2.6, but this was attributed to an electric surcharge, justifying the use of the next lowest peak, which is reported in Table 1. The records shown in Figs. 2 and 3 are not the recorded table motions (those are available only in low-resolution plots). They are estimates produced by scaling the El Centro-NS earthquake record to match the recorded value of the Housner Intensity provided by Çeçen. The peaks of the approximated peaks match reasonably well with the reported peaks given that shake tables do not reproduce input signals perfectly and that artificial acceleration spikes were reported in the later tests.

Table 1: Maximum recorded table accelerations (g)

Test	Reported	Approximated	Test	Reported	Approximated
H1-1	0.36	0.42	H2-1	0.17	0.17
H1-2	0.84	0.92	H2-2	0.33	0.35
H1-3	1.6	1.32	H2-3	0.49	0.53
			H2-4	0.47	0.53
			H2-5	0.72	0.79
			H2-6	1.0	1.05
			H2-7	1.6*	1.32

*Second highest peak

Figure 2: Estimated table accelerations for specimen H1

Figure 3: Estimated table accelerations for specimen H2

Description of damage to specimen

Table 2 summarizes the damage descriptions:

Table 2: Maximum recorded table accelerations

Test	Damage
H1-1	Cracks within the first stories, ~0.05mm.
H1-2	Crack widths were around 0.2 mm. No appreciable damage was observed in member mid-spans except for the flexural cracks on some columns.
H1-3	The crack widths were around 0.4 mm. Some cracks were observed at tenth and ninth levels. Crushing and spalling of the beam ends, especially at sixth and seventh story levels were seen. There were practically no new cracks at the base columns. All the cracks were of flexural type. The damage in this test was described as similar to but somewhat less than that of test H2-7.
H2-1	The shrinkage cracks developed more, but no major new crack developed during this run.
H2-2	Some of the shrinkage cracks opened up more. All the crack widths observed so far remained within 0.05 mm.
H2-3	Some flexural cracks developed on the base columns. The crack widths did not exceed 0.1 mm.
H2-4	The crack pattern remained practically the same at the end of the fourth run.
H2-5	The few cracks of this run were of flexure type and developed mostly on the beam ends of the stories four through eight. The crack widths were around 0.3 mm.
H2-6	The new cracks developed mainly on the beam ends of the third, fourth and ninth stories. There were a few cracks on the tenth story too. The crack widths were around 0.4 mm.
H2-7	Some crushing and spalling of concrete at beam ends of the sixth and seventh stories was observed at the end of this seventh run. This damage was described as “extensive” and P-Delta effects of up to 10% were reported.

Global and interstory drift

Values for roof drift (DR) and maximum interstory drifts (Dmax) are summarized in Table 3 along with the ratio of the two.

Table 3: Largest recorded roof (DR) and story (Dmax) drifts (any story)

Test	DR	Dmax	Dmax/DR	Test	DR	Dmax	Dmax/DR
H1-1	0.01	0.017	1.7	H2-1	0.003	0.006	2.0
H1-2	0.021	0.035	1.7	H2-2	0.007	0.013	1.9
H1-3	0.039	0.05	1.3	H2-3	0.01	0.015	1.5
				H2-4	0.01	0.015	1.5
				H2-5	0.016	0.022	1.4
				H2-6	0.024	0.039	1.6
				H2-7	0.039	0.056	1.4

Estimated displacement ductility

We can estimate ductility using curves for maximum base shear and base moment vs maximum roof deflection (Fig. 4), the yield roof displacement is about 15 mm (drift of about 0.65%). The maximum displacement is about 85 mm. The ratio of these two quantities implies an average displacement ductility slightly less than 6.

Figure 4: Estimated yield and maximum displacement, based on Fig. 5.14 in the thesis [C72a]

Measured period

A free vibration test was conducted before each run to determine the frequency, which is reported here as period (Table 4). The difference in the initial periods of the two specimens was attributed to less shrinkage cracking in specimen H2.

Table 4: Measured Period

Test	Period [s]	Test	Period [s]
H1-1	0.33	H2-1	0.23
H1-2	0.45	H2-2	0.30
H1-3	0.56	H2-3	0.38
		H2-4	0.43
		H2-5	0.43
		H2-6	0.50
		H2-7	0.53

Scaled tests on five-story lightly reinforced wall structure

Description of specimen

General:

This test series formed part of the European ECOLEADER test series and was conducted at the Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, in Lisbon, Portugal from 2003-2005. The tests investigated buildings with a large number of walls, resulting in a low force demand for each wall. In such cases, steel reinforcement is determined by the minimum limits. These walls are not ductile. Even if ductile flexural detailing were provided, it is argued that these walls will not benefit because the walls are not well anchored into the soil to allow the formation of a plastic hinge [B07a]. Despite the non-ductile detailing, the walls can function well as long as the force demand is not exceeded. During the 2010 Chile earthquake, compression and shear failures were observed in this type of system, but this is believed to be due to misuse of the system beyond its limits (increasing height while keeping walls thin and edges lightly confined) [F14a]. In this ECOLEADER test program, two similar tests were conducted, one to French design standards and one to Slovenian design standards. The results herein are from the latter.

Figure 5: Test specimen [F17a]

Geometry ($x = \text{flanges}$, $y = \text{web}$):

The model (Fig. 5) was designed to a scale factor of 1/3 by which lengths are divided by 3, stresses and accelerations are preserved, additional masses are applied to preserve the similitude of mass, time is divided by $\sqrt{3}= 1.732$, and thus ordinates of acceleration spectra are preserved and periods are reduced by the time factor [B07a]. The global geometry of the model is [F17a, corroborated by L16a]:

- Story height = 0.9m (to top of slab), total height = 4.5m (5 stories)
- All walls are 60 mm thick
- Flange [x-direction] is 1.60 m long (0.77 m clear on each side)
- Web [y-direction] is 1.56 m long with a 0.27 m x 0.67 m opening (webs are 0.585 m clear for each segment on either side of the opening)
- Slabs are 80 mm thick (1.60m x 1.56m in area)

Boundary regions were 115 mm long and web horizontal and vertical reinforcement was 0.24% ($\Phi 3/100$ mm). Reinforcement in boundary regions was 1.6% ($4\Phi 6$ mm) and 0.24% ($\Phi 3/100$ mm) for vertical and horizontal reinforcement, respectively [F17a]. “The length of the boundary regions is relatively short 11.5 cm (4.5 in.), which corresponds to 7% of the wall length. This is half of the length defined according to EC8 standard” [F17a]. The coupling beam was 60 mm wide and 0.23 m high with the following reinforcement: $2\Phi 6$ mm longitudinally at the top and bottom, $\Phi 3/50$ mm transversely, and $2 \times 1\Phi 6$ mm diagonally [F17a]. The slab has an edge beam on each of the free edges [L16].

Material properties [F17a]:

The mean compressive strength of concrete was 38.8 MPa (5.63 ksi). The compression strength of concrete used in the walls ranged from 34.2 MPa to 43.2 MPa (mean value was 39.2 and 38.3 MPa for all specimens and that corresponding to the first story, respectively). Two types of reinforcing bar were used. “The 6-mm (0.24-in.) bars for the main longitudinal reinforcement were ductile (their average ultimate strain was $\epsilon_{su} = 8.8\%$), having a yield strength $f_{sy} = 483$ MPa (70.05 ksi) and ultimate strength $f_{su} = 631$ MPa (91.52 ksi). Only brittle reinforcement ($\epsilon_{su} = 1.5\%$) having $f_{sy} = 786$ MPa (114.00 ksi) and $f_{su} = 826$ MPa (119.80 ksi) were available for the 3-mm (0.12-in.) bars in the web.”

Design process for specimen

“The model represented a typical apartment building built in the 1990s in Europe or Chile, with the important exception of the slab, which was considerably thicker compared to the prototype building and stiffened by steel blocks providing the additional mass” [F17a]. These buildings, with thin walls, a high wall-to-floor ratio (walls used as partitions as well as structurally) and used in moderate seismic regions, are governed by minimum reinforcement, not the seismic design load [F14a, F17a]. In the present case, minimum reinforcement was provided according to the Slovenian standard [F14a].

Description of ground motions

The Tolmezzo accelerogram, recorded during the Friuli 1976 earthquake, was used because it is typical for the region of interest and approximates the design spectrum: Type 1/Soil B spectrum in EC8. Both components (loading was biaxial) were modified to match the EC8 spectrum [F17a]. There were six ground motions. The first three were for calibration. Table control was poor in several cases, failing to match desired peak accelerations or spectra well [F17a]. Vertical acceleration was recorded and found to be non-negligible [L16]. The maximum accelerations measured on the shake table are [F17a] shown in Table 5. The records (with the reduced time scale) are shown in Fig. 6. These are obtained directly from the test data, sampled at 100 Hz (time step of 0.01 s).

Table 5: recorded table accelerations (g)

Test	Flanges [x]	Web [y]
T1	0.30	0.00
T2	0.00	0.16
T3	0.29	0.16
T4	0.42	0.33
T5	0.42	0.73
T6	0.52	1.02

Figure 6: Recorded table accelerations parallel to the web

Description of damage to specimen

The observed damage is summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Observed Test Damage

Test	X (Flanges)	Y (web)
T4	Minor cracking [L16a]; No significant inelastic behavior [F14a]; moderate cracking [F17a]	No damage [L16a; F17a]; No significant inelastic behavior [F14a]
T5	Further cracking [L16a]; moderate inelastic response and considerable lifting of the piers [F14a]; vertical bars yielded [F14a]	Diagonal cracks opened up near the opening [L16a]; moderate inelastic response [F14a]; damaged [F17a]. Analysis suggests that aggregate interlock began to deteriorate, thus activating horizontal reinforcement, which remained elastic [F14a].
T6	Damage due to web punching through [L16a]; large shear cracks opened up in the flanges of the first floor [F14a]; The dowel capacity of the weak longitudinal reinforcement in the central part of the flange was exhausted. Consequently, this part of the flange was considerably damaged, predominantly due to the punching of the web through it [F17a]	Diagonal shear failure, web punched through flange, fracture of two horizontal bars in web; no damage to coupling beam [L16a]; At the moment of the shear failure, a large crack opened in the web and its upper part was pushed against the flange [F17a]; Analysis suggests loss of aggregate interlock and failure of brittle horizontal bars. [F14a]; Practically no damage was observed in the coupling beams [F17a], No flexural damage was observed at the free end of the web in the T-piers next to the openings [F17a]

In all tests but the last, no significant effect of biaxial loading was found. This was attributed to limited yielding. However, the final simultaneous failure of both webs was attributed to biaxial loading [F17a]. Analysis results showed that at the time of the failure, both webs were in net tension. This is consistent with the crack inclination in both piers [F14a]. Such tension significantly reduced shear capacity [F17a].

No damage was observed at the openings in the web. Analysis showed that this was due to strong coupling (stiff coupling beam, with a height-to-length ratio of approximately 1, and interaction with the thick slab). The specimen behaved more like a wall with openings, with moderate demand at the base of the opening [F17a].

Global and interstory drift table [L16a]

The table below summarizes roof drift (DR), first-story drift (D1), and the ratio between the two for each direction of testing. These values were calculated directly from the data and corroborated in the case of roof drift for the last three ground motions by documented results [L16a]. In general, the bottom story drift was larger than roof drift in the y-direction and smaller in the x-direction.

Table 7: Largest recorded roof (DR) and 1st story (D1) drifts

Test	X (Flanges)			Y (web)		
	DR	D1	D1/DR	DR	D1	D1/DR
T1	0.12%	0.12%	1.00	0.02%	0.11%	*
T2	0.02%	0.09%	*	0.04%	0.11%	2.57
T3	0.13%	0.12%	0.93	0.03%	0.10%	3.06
T4	0.24%	0.19%	0.82	0.08%	0.13%	1.67
T5	0.32%	0.32%	1.00	0.29%	0.33%	1.16
T6	0.59%	0.52%	0.87	0.77%	2.23%	2.90

*Not reported because there was no excitation in that direction rendering the ratio meaningless

Estimated displacement ductility

Based on data for base shear and roof deflection and an approximated bilinear fit to the data (Fig. 7), the displacement ductility achieved in Test 6 was approximately 2. The estimated yield displacement is 1.5 cm and the estimated final displacement is 3.2 cm.

Measured period [F17a]

The periods summarized in Table 8 were obtained by free vibration tests.

Table 8: Measured Period

Test	Period [s]	
	X (Flanges)	Y (Web)
Before T1	0.167	0.139
Before T2	0.183	0.142
Before T3	0.183	0.142
Before T4	0.186	0.151
Before T5	0.228	0.174
Before T6	0.244	0.213
After T6	0.262	0.444

Figure 7: Data and bilinear fit for the final test

Full-scale tests on seven-story wall building

Description of specimen

General:

The specimen represented a full-scale slice of a 7-story RC residential building. Lateral resistance was provided by a load-bearing wall. The perpendicular walls provided transverse and torsional stability but were detailed so that they could rock out of plane. Testing was conducted at UCSD LHPOST, from October 2005 to January 2006. The information summarized in this report is a composite of two papers [P11a, P11b].

Geometry:

The specimen is shown in Fig. 8. The total building height was 19.201 m, with story heights of 2.743m. The web wall measured 3.66 m long and was 0.20 m thick at the first and seventh levels and 0.15 m elsewhere. The slabs were 0.20 m thick.

Material properties:

Based on material tests, the average yield strength of reinforcing steel was 455 MPa, average yield strength of resistance weld confining reinforcement was 518 MPa, and average concrete compressive strength was 37.9 MPa.

Design process for specimen

The building was designed with a displacement-based, performance-based method at two performance levels: Life Safety (LS) and Immediate Occupancy (IO). The criteria for IO were (1) maximum tensile strain of 1% in the wall longitudinal reinforcement; (2) maximum compressive strain of 0.4% in the concrete; and (3) maximum interstory drift ratio of 1%. The criteria for LS were (1) maximum tensile strain of 5% in the longitudinal reinforcement and (2) maximum roof drift ratio of 3%. The following special detailing was employed in this building for evaluation: (1) reduction in the longitudinal reinforcement; (2) use of a single curtain of reinforcement to transfer shear; (3) constraint of plasticity to the first level of the wall; and (4) use of resistance-welded reinforcement in the boundary elements of the first level of the walls. Regarding item 3: “The spread of plasticity in the walls of the building is deliberately precluded from extending beyond the first floor by special detailing of the longitudinal reinforcement. The spread of plasticity in the wall is constrained for two reasons: (1) to optimize construction, and (2) to reduce the uncertainty in estimating the plastic hinge length. Constraining the plastic hinge length to within the base of the wall allows for special reinforcing detailing only in the bottom part of the walls.”

Figure 8: Test specimen [P11a]

Description of ground motions

The building was subjected to four historical records recorded in two Southern California earthquakes. EQ1 was low intensity (25% smaller than the IO spectrum in the relevant period range), EQ2 and EQ3 were medium intensity, and EQ4 was high intensity (matching the design basis earthquake for LS in the relevant period range). These records are detailed in Table 9 and Fig. 9.

Table 9: Details of selected ground motions, accelerations and velocities are those produced by the shake table (Vmax is maximum velocity)

Test	Event	Station	Component	PGA [g]	Vmax [cm/s]
EQ1	1971 San Fernando	Van Nuys	Longitudinal	0.15	26
EQ2	1971 San Fernando	Van Nuys	Transverse	0.27	32
EQ3	1994 Northridge	Woodland Hills	Longitudinal	0.35	43
EQ4	1994 Northridge	Sylmar Olive View	360	0.91	102

Figure 9: Recorded table accelerations

Description of damage to specimen

The damage descriptions are summarized in Table 10. The reported level of nonlinearity was determined by strain measurements.

Table 10: Damage descriptions

Test	Damage
EQ1	Slightly nonlinear. Maximum curvature (web wall) less than yield curvature.
EQ2	Moderately nonlinear
EQ3	Moderately nonlinear
EQ4	Highly nonlinear. Concrete spalling was observed, but no evidence was found of longitudinal bar buckling. "limited damage" no "obvious life-safety hazards". "The building might not be immediately operational, but would require only minimum repairs."

Global and interstory drift table

The following table summarizes the measured roof drift (DR), maximum interstory drift (Dmax), and the ratio between the two:

Table 11: Largest recorded roof (DR) and story (Dmax) drifts (any story)

Test	DR [%]	Dmax [%]	Dmax/DR
EQ1	0.28	0.35	1.25
EQ2	0.75	0.89	1.19
EQ3	0.83	1.03	1.24
EQ4	2.06	2.36	1.15

Estimated displacement ductility

We estimate displacement ductility in two ways. First is the description of damage, which indicates little nonlinearity in EQ1 and moderate nonlinearity for EQ2. The yield point for a bilinear approximation would fall between these two. We will estimate the value at 0.6. Dividing the drift of EQ4 by 0.6 gives an estimated ductility of about 3.4. The second method used the moment-roof drift curve and an approximate bilinear fit [P11b] (the moment curve was used because the bulk of deformation was attributed to flexure and the shear curve was erratic). Using maximum and yield drifts of 0.39 and 0.13, respectively, the ductility is about 3. Both methods justify a ductility slightly larger than 3.

Fig 10: Moment-displacement data [P11b] and bilinear fit

Measured period

White noise tests were used to determine the periods reported in Table 12.

Table 12: Measured period

Test	Period [s]	Test	Period [s]
Before EQ1	0.59	Before EQ4	0.88
Before EQ2	0.65	After EQ4	1.16
Before EQ3	0.82		

Full-scale tests on five-story frame building

Description of specimen

General:

The building is a full-scale, five-story, RC building furnished with a variety of non-structural components and systems. It was tested as part of the BNCS test series in 2012 at the UCSD LHPOST facility. It is a cast-in-place special moment frame (with shear walls transverse to the direction of shaking) [C16a].

Geometry:

The specimen is pictured in Fig. 11. Plan dimensions are 6.6m x 11.0m (21.5 ft x 36 ft), split into 2 bays in the shaking direction, with floor heights = 14' (4.27 m) and a total height = 70' (21.34 m). The longer plan direction corresponds to the direction of shaking.

Fig 11: Test specimen [C16a]

Lateral frame beams were 300mm x 700 mm, detailed differently at each floor, but all to the same moment capacity of 390 kN-m. Second and third floors used high strength reinforcement, fourth and fifth used ductile rods at the beam-column joints. Fourth-floor beams also incorporated hybrid frame details. These details have proven stable, ductile performance in previous tests. The roof beam used prescriptive details per ACI 318-08. Beam shear reinforcement was (#4) @ 102 mm 4" on near the column face, and at 152mm (6") in the remaining beam. Slabs were 200 mm thick with openings of 2.3 m x 4.2 m and 2.1 m x 2.6 m for stairs and an elevator and miscellaneous circular openings 100 mm – 250 mm in diameter. Columns were 460 mm x 660 mm with a longitudinal reinforcement ratio of 1.42% [C16a].

Material properties:

Compressive strength f'_c was specified at 40 MPa (5 ksi) for 28-day strength. Average f'_c in MPa, for columns/walls and slabs/beam, respectively, was 44.1 and 39.3 at 28 days, 57.2 and 51.7 at start of (base isolated) testing. Modulus in GPa was 32.6 and 33.1, respectively, at the start of testing.

Design process for specimen

The specimen was designed for a Southern California location where site-specific ground motions were available. These were developed for site class D (stiff) soil, with $S_{MS} = 2.10g$ and $S_{m1} = 1.43g$. The building was designed by performance-based methods with a maximum interstory drift ratio of 2.5% and a maximum floor acceleration of 0.8g. Seven spectrum-matched records were used for the MCE scenario and three for serviceability. One of the MCE earthquakes (Denali) was subsequently used in the test series [C13a].

Description of ground motions

Table 13, a composite from two sources [P16a, C16a], lists details of the ground motion. The Denali motions were matched to 100% and 67% of the design response spectrum for the selected site and the two Northridge motions were matched to 20% of the target maximum spectrum [C16a]. The ICA records were used unmodified. The motions produced by the shake table are shown in Fig. 12. These are obtained from the data using only one of the four accelerometers at the base. All four sensors were reported to produce practically equal results [P13a], justifying the use of just one. The following are the details of the sensor used ([P13b]):

- Sensor name: UA33E31
- Channel: 69
- Channel sensitivity: 4.77793E-7 (g/raw unit)
- File names (all terminate with “.UCLA2.txt”): 20120507232631, 20120509202245, 20120509232420, 20120511180934, 20120515181932, 20120516015512

Table 13: Details of ground motions and accelerations produced by shake table

Test	Station	Scale (%)	Earthquake	PGA (g)	Dur* [s]	Sa 0.2	Sa 1.0
FB1	Canoga Park	100	1994 Northridge	0.21	15	0.42	0.34
FB2	LA City Terrace	100	1994 Northridge	0.18	20	0.42	0.29
FB3	ICA	50	2007 Pisco-Peru	0.21	91	0.35	0.48
FB4	ICA	100	2007 Pisco-Peru	0.26	96	0.46	0.48
FB5	Pump Station #9	67	2002 Denali	0.64	49	1.50	1.10
FB6	Pump Station #9	100	2002 Denali	0.80	49	1.60	1.40

*Strong Motion Duration

Fig 12: Recorded table accelerations for the chosen sensor. These are the raw, unfiltered records with long sections of either ambient or white noise included.

Description of damage to specimen

The damage descriptions in Table 14 are from [P13a] if not otherwise specified:

Table 14: Observed damage

Test	Damage
FB1	No damage
FB2	No damage
FB3	Minor, small cracking
FB4	Minor, small cracking
FB5	Moderate, onset of spalling, widening of cracks at column bases, slab and around columns and beams, some rebar yielding
FB6	Severe. Extensive network of concrete cracking, spalling in structural elements at multiple levels, yielding and fracturing of rebar within the moment frame beams at floors two and three and punching shear failure at the slabs surrounding the columns at floors two and three. Temporary shoring was required to allow safe access to the building. [P13a]. Bar fracture was confirmed to have occurred at a peak drift ratio of about 6% [C16a]

Global and interstory drift table

Drifts (Table 15) were digitized from values reported graphically [C16a, Fig. 18]. The drifts reported in the figure were obtained by double integration of accelerations after verifying the method verified with independent measurements from string potentiometers [P13a]. Peak drift ratios occurred in the second story [C16a].

Table 15: Largest recorded roof (DR) and story (Dmax) drifts (any story)

Test	DR [%]	Dmax [%]	Dmax/DR
FB1	0.32	0.48	1.48
FB2	0.35	0.57	1.62
FB3	0.60	0.95	1.59
FB4	0.94	1.42	1.50
FB5	1.79	2.75	1.54
FB6	3.04	5.99	1.97

Estimated displacement ductility

Displacement ductility is estimated in two ways. First, based on observed behavior, it is assumed that the yield point falls between tests FB3 and FB4. Dividing the maximum roof drift FB6 by the average roof drift of FB3 and FB4, estimated displacement ductility is 3.9. The second way is by using reported values of maximum base shear in each test, which have been digitized from the appropriate figure [C16a, Fig 21]. From an approximated bilinear fit to the base shear vs drift data (Fig. 13), using a yield drift of 0.75%, the estimated displacement ductility is 4.1. From both of these approaches, it is concluded that the displacement ductility reached in the final test was about 4.

Fig 13: Base-shear vs roof drift data and bilinear fit.

Measured period

Measured periods (Table 16) were taken from Chen [C16a]. Periods reported in the literature were determined by roof-to-ground undamped spectral ratios. The periods after FB5 and FB6 were not reported. The white noise and pulse data from the experiment was used to estimate the former in a quick, rudimentary manner. Channel 9 (roof acceleration) in the data was used for this purpose. Fourier response spectra of white noise excitation before FB6 exhibited a peak at a period of 1.55 s. The pulse data exhibited varying period (shorter period each subsequent cycle) but averaging 1.5 sec over the first six cycles. Based on these considerations, an estimated period of 1.5 was selected for the structure after FB5 (prior to FB6).

Table 16: Measured periods

Test	Period [s]	Note
Before FB1 AV	0.52	From text
Before FB1 WN	0.74	From text
After FB1	0.89	Digitized from [C16a] fig 14
After FB2	0.89	Digitized from [C16a] fig 14
After FB3	1.21	Digitized from [C16a] fig 14
After FB4	1.41	Digitized from [C16a] fig 14
After FB5	1.5	From white noise data
After FB6	NA	

References

Çeçen

- [C72a] Çeçen, H. (1972). Response of Ten Story, Reinforced Concrete Model Frames to Simulated Earthquakes, Doctoral Thesis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.

Lisbon

- [B07a] Bisch, P. & Coin, A (2007). “Seismic Behaviour of Slightly Reinforced Concrete Walls: Experiments and Theoretical Conclusions”, *Bull Earthquake Eng* 5(1): 45–65. DOI: 10.1007/s10518-006-9014-1.
- [F14a] Fischinger M., Rejec K., Isaković T. (2014) Inelastic Shear Response of RC Walls: A Challenge in Performance Based Design and Assessment. In: Fischinger M. (eds) Performance-Based Seismic Engineering: Vision for an Earthquake Resilient Society. Geotechnical, Geological and Earthquake Engineering, vol 32. Springer, Dordrecht.
- [F17a] Fishinger, M., Kante, P., and Isakovic, T, (2017). “Shake Table Response of a Coupled RC Wall with Thin T-Shaped Piers”, *J. Struct. Eng.* 143(5): 04017004.
- [L16a] Lu, Y. and Panagiotou, M. (2016). “Three-dimensional beam-truss model for reinforced concrete walls and slabs – part 2: modeling approach and validation for slabs and coupled walls, *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics*, 45(11): 1707-1724, DOI: 10.1002/eqe.2720.

UCSD 7

- [P11a] Panagiotou, M. and Restrepo, José I. (2011). “Displacement-Based Method of Analysis for Regular Reinforced-Concrete Wall Buildings: Application to a Full-Scale 7-Story Building Slice Tested at UC–San Diego”, *J. Structural Engineering*, 136(6):677-690.
- [P11b] Panagiotou, M., Restrepo, José I., and Conte, Joel P. (2011). “Shake-Table Test of a Full-Scale 7-Story Building Slice. Phase I: Rectangular Wall”, *J. Structural Engineering*, 136(6):691-704.

UCSD 5

- [C13a] Chen, M., Pantoli, E., Wang, X. Astroza, R., Ebrahimian, H., Mintz, S., Hutchinson, T., Conte, J., Restrepo, J., Meacham, B., Kim, J., Park, H-J (2013). BNCS Report #1: Full-scale structural and nonstructural building system performance during earthquakes and post-earthquake fire – specimen design, construction, and test protocol, SSRP-13/09, UCSD Department of Structural Engineering.
- [C16a] Chen, M., Pantoli, E., Wang, X. Astroza, R., Ebrahimian, H., Hutchinson, T., Conte, J., Restrepo, J., Marin, C., Walsh, K., Bachman, R., Hoehler, M., Englekirk, R., and Faghihi, M. (2016). “Full-Scale Structural and Nonstructural Building System Performance during Earthquakes: Part I – Specimen Description, Test Protocol, and Structural Response”, *Earthquake Spectra* 32(2):737-770.
- [P13a] Pantoli, E., Chen, M., Wang, X. Astroza, R., Ebrahimian, H., Mintz, S., Hutchinson, T., Conte, J., Restrepo, J., Meacham, B., Kim, J., Park, H-J (2013). BNCS Report #2: Full-scale structural and nonstructural building system performance during earthquakes and post-earthquake fire – test results, SSRP-13/10, UCSD Department of Structural Engineering.
- [P13b] Pantoli, E., Chen, M., Hutchinson, T., Restrepo, J. (2013). BNCS Report #3: Full-scale structural and nonstructural building system performance during earthquakes and post-earthquake fire – camera and analog sensor details, SSRP-13/11, UCSD Department of Structural Engineering.

[P16a] Pantoli, E., Chen, M., Hutchinson, T., Astroza, R., Conte, J., Ebrahimian, H. Restrepo, J., and Wang, X. (2016). “Landmark Data Set from the Building Nonstructural Components and Systems (BNCS) Project”, *Earthquake Spectra* 32(2):1239–1259.